

DOI: 10.31866/2410-1915.20.2019.172386

UDC 378.015.3:005.32]:81'243-047.23

MOTIVATION AS ONE OF THE MOST EFFECTIVE WAYS OF OPTIMIZING FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

Maryna Antonivska

*Lecturer,**ORCID: 0000-0002-4451-3735, antonivska_maryna@ukr.net,**Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts,**36, Ye. Konovaltsia Str., Kyiv, 01133, Ukraine*

The purpose of the work is to consider the most important conditions and ways of forming positive sustainable motivation of students' educational activities, identify key aspects, analyze peculiarities of different methodologies and newest motivational approaches concerning the issue of foreign languages study. The research methodology consisted in the application of such research methods as study, analysis and generalization with the purpose of revealing the concept of motivation as one of the most effective ways of optimizing foreign language learning process. Scientific novelty of the work is to determine the role of the teacher in the process of overcoming communicative deviations on the basis of linguocultural differences and structuring some psychological and pedagogical aspects of motivation as an integral component of the foreign language study, which are considered in this article. Also, the article explicitly outlines and suggests concrete ways and methods for the formation and development of sustainable positive motivation. It is believed that content consistency during the process of studying, methods of teaching, consideration of students' cognitive needs and interests are the main factors in the process of educational motivation formation and these elements strengthen all components of motivation: needs, aspirations, interests, emotions, motives themselves, which in turn contribute to the deepening and expansion of the sphere of students' cognitive activity.

Conclusions. Consequently, we considered some of the most important, in our opinion, conditions and ways of forming positive, stable motivation for students' educational activities. To establish such a motivation, one should use not only one way, but all ways, methods in a certain system, in a complex, because none of them, without others, can play a decisive role in the formation of motivation.

Consistency of the educational content and ways of filling it with cognitive needs and students interests counteracts the formation of a negative educational result. Optimally selected material strengthens all components of motivation: needs, aspirations, interests, emotions, motives themselves. Formation of a stable motivation level requires teacher to select appropriate educational materials that would represent cognitive, communicative, professional values, stimulate mental activity, and promote deepening and expansion of cognitive students' activity.

Keywords: motivation; foreign language; English; educational process; foreign language learning; foreign conceptual sphere.

Introduction

Integration of Ukraine into European community requires emergence of new qualities of Ukrainian society, emergence of “new people” – educated, sincere, highly skilled specialists with knowledge of two or more foreign languages. A significant increase in international relations creates certain preconditions for improving foreign languages studying process.

After all, knowledge of foreign languages is a real evidence of cultural and educational level. The scope of their application for modern human is greatly expanded with the increase of interstate ties, as well as the possibility of using foreign materials in their work.

Therefore, the issue of motivation in the process of foreign languages studying becomes relevant and important. Psychologists claim that one of the most urgent issues of proper pedagogy is development and constant support of educational activity, development of favorable emotional climate during foreign language classes (Ilin, 2000, p.385).

The main difficulty in the process of foreign language studying is a lack of motivation. Foreign language is a special system of thinking, new image of the world, because language is a means of perception.

Motivation is the most important foundation for success in the process of languages learning. This is the main driving force behind student’s work.

Motivation is characterized, above all, by students’ interest to the subject being studied and their desire and willingness to study it.

Interest contributes to concentration, stimulates the repetition of the studied material, as well as enriches the extra-linguistic knowledge of students, thereby contributing to the formation of their general competence. Researchers define motivation as one particular motive, and as a single system of motives, and as a special sphere, which includes needs, motives, goals, interests in their complex interplay and interaction. The complexity and multidimensionality of motivation problem determines the plurality of approaches to understanding its essence, nature, structure, as well as methods of its study.

Concerning the theory of motivation issue, analysis of special literature shows that this issue is under active discussion. The main points of the discussion relate to the interpretation of the concept itself, main components and types of motivation, as well as the search for optimal ways of producing motivation as one of the main components of foreign language studying.

Theoretical and methodological basis of the study was composed of modern sociological, cultural, psychological and pedagogical ideas and concepts of foreign language teaching, interaction between the process of studying and motivation, the leading role of motivation in the process of foreign language studying.

At various times, a lot of foreign and domestic researchers, scientists investigated problems of motivation, contributed to the development of this problem and carried out an analysis of the motivation process, in particular: M. Covington, R. Gardner, J. Harmer, W. Lambert, G. Crookes, R. Schmidt, modern approaches to the problems of motivation and tried to analyze different types of motivation.

Such scientists as A. Leontiev, N. Symonova determined motivation as the way to encourage students to learn and explore foreign language, improve and develop needs and desire to understand foreign language.

Some psychological and pedagogical aspects of motivation as a component of foreign language studying are considered in this article, concrete ways and methods of stable positive motivation formation and development are offered. It is believed that content consistency during the process of studying, methods of teaching, consideration of students' cognitive needs and interests are the main factors in the process of educational motivation formation and these elements strengthen all components of motivation: needs, aspirations, interests, emotions, motives themselves, which in turn contribute to the deepening and expansion of the sphere of students' cognitive activity.

The purpose of the article

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to consider the most important conditions and ways of forming positive sustainable motivation of students' educational activities, identify key aspects, analyze peculiarities of different methodologies and newest motivational approaches concerning the issue of foreign languages study.

Achieving this goal involves solving the following tasks:

- to study existing approaches to understanding the phenomenon of «motivation» and its impact on the students' desire to learn foreign language;
- to reveal pedagogical essence and specificity of the motivation influence on the processes of students' self-determination;
- to determine the criteria for the successful motivation, identify patterns and principles that influence the increase in the effectiveness of motivation.

Presentation of the main material

Correct selection of motivational actions methods in the learning process will allow to change the result in the better way and make the process of studying more effective. In order to create selection process more successful, one must clearly understand the essence of the very motivation in the field of foreign languages studying, its varieties, approaches to it and the sequence of motivational actions implementation.

Motivation in the process of foreign languages studying by its nature is a set of actions that teacher uses to initiate, interest and activate learning groups to achieve learning efficiency (Latyshev, 2003, p.54).

There are external and several types of internal motivation. External motivation, usually, tends to target students to achieve the final result. Internal motivation has a strong stimulating effect on the learning process (Ziazium, 1999, p.4). And for this purpose it is necessary to establish a process of studying with such a degree, so that those who study language might feel the result and progress towards their goal. In addition to well-known external and internal

types of motivation, in foreign psychology and pedagogy are differentiated situational, global and instrumental motivation (Hrabovska, 2002, p.14). Studies have shown that all types of motivation are necessary during the process of foreign language studying.

O. Tarnopolskiy (13) points out that practically all students have a promising internal motivation, because they completely understand the importance of foreign language knowledge for their life and career. The influence of procedural motivation is completely different, because it is associated with pleasure from the very process of activity, therefore, when it manages to form it (procedural motivation) in the process of learning the language, the success in the learning process is largely guaranteed.

In foreign theory and practice, the theory of «purposeful motivation» is very popular, the components of which are: internal (core) motivation – feelings, desires, efforts; orientation towards learning and attitude to the learning situation (Gardner, 1972).

Gardner recognizes two orientations for language learning:

– *instrumental*, which is associated with the learner's desire to learn a language in order to achieve such a purpose, as exam preparation or career development;

– *integrative*, which is associated with learner's desire to study language through a high positive personal attitude to this language, people who communicate this particular language, culture, etc.

Nowadays there exist a lot of modern approaches to the problem of motivation. Each approach has its principles and each has a necessity of motivational provision towards the process of foreign language learning. The majority of scientists, researchers, teachers claim that there are three motivational blocks during the lesson:

1. At the beginning of the lesson, the main motive or motivational composition is activated, with which the whole activity is logically related;
2. At the end of the lesson, operational and perspective motivation is used, that is, the presentation of material for the next lesson;
3. During the whole lesson the motivational support of the teacher is the main component.

Motivation should become that point of support, on which all the content of the lesson is based. For this purpose, teacher should be a good scriptwriter, director and actor. Therefore, the development of an effective system for the formation of foreign-language professional competence of future specialists is possible only in case of theoretical and methodological basis and consideration of psychological characteristics and reserve learning opportunities of those who are studying.

Teacher's orientation towards students of intermediate level is a dominant characteristic of a traditional pedagogic system of foreign language teaching in higher educational establishments. Such an approach reduces the individualization of education, does not take into account the activation of students' reserve learning opportunities, which leads to the disappearance of desire to continue the process of foreign language studying.

The reason for motivation emergence in the most general sense is a certain need that is created on the basis of contradictions between what a person has, or possesses, what has achieved and what a person does not have, does not possess, has not achieved. The desire to have, possess, achieve, constitutes the content of need. And if the sphere of such needs falls into foreign language learning, they become a motive for its assimilation.

The motivation-inductive sphere can be influenced primarily by social motives, determined by the needs of society. Secondly, motivational-inductive sphere of a person can be influenced by the nature of its activities.

The action of external and internal factors of motivation must be balanced, so teacher should understand that extremes here are undesirable. Absolutism of internal interest limits student's actual possibilities, and dry approach from the standpoint of external requirements deprives emotional dimension from the process of learning.

Finally, teacher should remember that motivation should be considered not as a short-term factor of activity, which can be discarded after reaching the goal. It is said that this process is stable and only enshrined in the process of language learning.

Since motivation is of great importance in the process of foreign language studying, it is important for the teacher to timely assist in its emergence, support and preserve it.

But for this teacher needs to find out and understand possible sources of motivation:

- student's awareness and acceptance of social necessity of foreign language studying;
- formation of students' personal needs to the process of foreign language studying;
- pleasure from the learning process, what is called the joy of knowledge.

In the formation of motives for foreign language learning and student's positive attitude to the subject, teacher can play an important role.

Here, first of all, it is about relations that have developed between teacher and each student in particular. If they are friendly, provide mutual help, motive of joy from studies has a favorable ground, and student's positive attitude to teacher is transferred to the subject.

However, in the social interpretation of foreign language learning motives, there is another aspect that deserves attention. In the process of learning, development and education, student strives for an ideal, which is formed and determined by the needs of society, its traditions and customs. The public sense of duty tells student the need to become a highly educated person, ready to perform those tasks that society can put in front of him.

In this regard, student's foreign language acquisition serves as an implementation of society needs, with which he should be considered as a citizen. Teacher's responsibility is to cover all these aspects in detail – both through the prism of foreign language functions in current events and on examples of people who perfectly know foreign language (diplomats, businessmen, lawyers, actors, singers, etc.).

Also, to create a stable positive motivation towards learning activity, it is very important for each student to feel as the subject of educational process. This can be facilitated by the personality-role form of educational process organization. In this form of organization, each student performs a particular role in the learning process, which contributes to the formation of this activity motivation. Thus, different forms of collective work make it possible to differentiate learning activities for different categories of students, to differentiate tasks so that they are feasible for each student, which in turn is important for the formation of learning motivation.

Processing of theoretical material on the problem of educational activity motivation has made it possible to state that the structure of educational activity motivation is not once and for all formed, it is constantly changing. Formation of motivation is a process exclusively internal. In fact, motivated learning activity can only be provided if there is a certain need and awareness of the student ability to meet this need, directing its activity to fulfill the educational task.

Teacher should remember that tasks should be communicative and creative in nature, which will meet the needs of a separate educational audience. The use of specially selected material based on the interests of students, their desire to assert itself as an adult, inclusion in the discussion of exciting problems using communicative and creative tasks will make learning personally significant, which is an integral attribute of a high level of motivation.

Modeling real life situations will make it possible to use language as a means, and not a goal that will correspond to situations of real communication. In today's methodology, it is widely believed that the role of teacher in performing communicative tasks does not decrease as much as it changes. Teacher should create the conditions for the most effective task, structuring it and asking for a certain impetus. Teacher should also interfere with work when a pause occurs and do so, basically by asking questions.

Teacher should propose tasks that will motivate them to support the conversation until the specific goal is achieved.

The greater concentration of students' attention on a motivated informal communication than on grammar gives a better result, since the work itself brings pleasure.

We want to emphasize that it's necessary for teachers to do the following things to increase the motivation of foreign language learning:

- 1) Modify educational program, taking into account requirements for Ukraine's entry into European educational space;

- 2) Select authentic materials, taking into account the specifics of students' future professional activity;

- 3) Since the prerequisite for successful student learning is communication, teacher needs to select the most up-to-date topics for discussion. Such communication is carried out in the form of conversation, which is considered as a special method of interpersonal communication, which lies between the extreme points of the dialogue and the monologue, and is a dialogic speech with the elements of different functional types monologues.

4) It is necessary to use various creative tasks and tests that help to systematize and deepen knowledge not only of foreign language, but also promote the development of students creative abilities. This task guarantees not only interest in learning and subject in particular, but also high efficiency, because students like tasks that allow them to demonstrate their creative abilities and skills.

5) Also, the key to the perfect learning of material is to watch movies of different genres, with further discussion and implementation of certain exercises on the acquisition of lexical material highlighted in the film.

6) Listening to music during the lesson is a great idea to encourage students to engage in a more in-depth study of a foreign language.

Conclusions

Consequently, we considered some of the most important, in our opinion, conditions and ways of forming positive, stable motivation for students' educational activities. To establish such a motivation, one should use not only one way, but all ways, methods in a certain system, in a complex, because none of them, without others, can play a decisive role in the formation of motivation.

Consistency of the educational content and ways of filing it with cognitive needs and students interests counteracts the formation of a negative educational result. Optimally selected material strengthens all components of motivation: needs, aspirations, interests, emotions, motives themselves. Formation of a stable motivation level requires teacher to select appropriate educational materials that would represent cognitive, communicative, professional values, stimulate mental activity, and promote deepening and expansion of cognitive students' activity.

Motivation determines the performance of educational activities and is an integral part of it. Approximation of linguistic activity in the classroom to real communication makes it possible to use language as means of communication, increases students interest in learning and to the language they learn. Thus, after conducting the appropriate changes, that is, successful selection of the methodology, its consistent and systematic implementation, there is expectation of obtaining results due to enhancement of motivation, increase of interest in studying foreign languages, overcoming of psychological barriers.

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The article was received in editors office: 29.03.2019

МОТИВАЦІЯ ЯК ОДИН З НАЙБІЛЬШ ЕФЕКТИВНИХ СПОСОБІВ ОПТИМІЗАЦІЇ ПРОЦЕСУ ВИВЧЕННЯ ІНОЗЕМНИХ МОВ У ЗАКЛАДАХ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ

Антонівська Марина Олександрівна

Викладач,

ORCID: 0000-0002-4451-3735, antonivska_maryna@ukr.net,

*Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв,
Київ, Україна*

Мета статті. Розглянути, виокремити та диференціювати найважливіші умови та шляхи формування позитивної стійкої мотивації навчальної діяльності студентів, визначити ключові аспекти, проаналізувати особливості різних освітніх методик та новітніх мотиваційних підходів до вивчення іноземних мов. Методологія дослідження базується на аналізі та узагальненні з метою виявлення концепції мотивації як одного з найбільш ефективних способів оптимізації процесу вивчення іноземної мови. Наукова новизна роботи полягає у визначенні ролі викладача в процесі подолання комунікативних девіацій на основі лінгвокультурних відмінностей та структуризації деяких психолого-педагогічних аспектів мотивації як невід'ємного компонента вивчення іноземної мови, які розглядаються в даній статті. Також у статті чітко окреслюються та пропонуються конкретні шляхи та методи формування та розвитку стійкої позитивної мотивації. Вважається, що послідовність змісту в процесі навчання, методика навчання, врахування пізнавальних потреб та інтересів студентів є основними факторами в процесі формування мотивації навчальної діяльності, і ці елементи зміцнюють всі складові мотивації: потреби, прагнення, інтереси, емоції, самі мотиви, які, у свою чергу, сприяють поглибленню і розширенню сфери пізнавальної діяльності студентів.

Висновки. Отже, ми розглянули деякі з найважливіших, на нашу думку, умов і способів формування позитивної, стійкої мотивації для покращення навчальної діяльності студентів. Для встановлення такої мотивації потрібно використовувати не тільки один спосіб, але й всі способи, методи в певній системі, в комплексі, тому що жодна з них, без інших, не може відігравати вирішальну роль у формуванні мотивації.

Послідовність змісту освіти та способи її подання з пізнавальними потребами та студентськими інтересами протидіє формуванню негативного освітнього результату. Оптимально підібраний матеріал посилює всі складові мотивації: потреби, прагнення, інтереси, емоції, самі мотиви. Формування стабільного мотиваційного рівня вимагає

від викладача вибирати відповідні навчальні матеріали, які б представляли когнітивні, комунікативні, професійні цінності, стимулювали розумову діяльність, сприяли поглибленню та розширенню пізнавальної діяльності студентів.

Ключові слова: мотивація; іноземна мова; англійська мова; навчальний процес; вивчення іноземної мови; іноземна концептуальна сфера.

МОТИВАЦИЯ КАК ОДИН ИЗ НАИБОЛЕЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ СПОСОБОВ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ПРОЦЕССА ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ

Антоновская Марина Александровна

Преподаватель,

ORCID: 0000-0002-4451-3735, antonivska_maryna@ukr.net,

*Киевский национальный университет культуры и искусств,
Киев, Украина*

Цель статьи. Рассмотреть, выделить и дифференцировать важнейшие условия и пути формирования положительной устойчивой мотивации учебной деятельности студентов, определить ключевые аспекты, проанализировать особенности различных образовательных методик и новейших мотивационных подходов к изучению иностранных языков. Методология исследования основана на анализе и обобщении с целью выявления концепции мотивации как одного из наиболее эффективных способов оптимизации процесса изучения иностранного языка. Научная новизна работы заключается в определении роли преподавателя в процессе преодоления коммуникативных девиаций на основе лингвокультурных различий и структуризации некоторых психолого-педагогических аспектов мотивации как неотъемлемого компонента изучения иностранного языка, которые рассматриваются в данной статье. Выводы. Итак, мы рассмотрели некоторые из важнейших, по нашему мнению, условий и способов формирования положительной, устойчивой мотивации для улучшения учебной деятельности студентов. Для установления такой мотивации следует использовать только один способ, но все способы, методы в определенной системе, в комплексе, так как ни одна из них, без помощи других, не может играть решающую роль в формировании мотивации.

Последовательность содержания образования и способы ее представления с познавательными потребностями и студенческими интересами противодействует формированию негативного образовательного результата. Оптимально подобранный материал усиливает все составляющие мотивации: потребности, стремления, интересы, эмоции, сами мотивы. Формирование стабильного мотивационного уровня требует от преподавателя выбирать соответствующие учебные материалы, которые бы представляли когнитивные, коммуникативные, профессиональные ценности, стимулировали умственную деятельность, способствовали углублению и расширению познавательной деятельности студентов.

Ключевые слова: мотивация; иностранный язык; английский язык; учебный процесс; изучение иностранного языка; иностранный концептуальная сфера.